

A study of Occupational Stress of Secondary School Teachers of Sonipat District in Relation to their Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to explore the relationship between Occupational Stress and Job Satisfaction among secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. A sample of 400 secondary school teachers of Sonipat District was chosen by random sampling technique. Out of 400 teachers 200 were from Government school teachers and 200 were from private schools. Both having 100 males and 100 females teacher. A descriptive survey method was used for the study to measuring the Occupational Stress, The Occupational Stress Index by Dr. A.K. Srivastava and A.P. Singh and for Job Satisfaction, Job Satisfaction scale by Dr. Meera Dixit were used for collecting the data. For analyzing the data descriptive statistical techniques namely mean, S.D., t-Test and Coefficient of correlation were used. The finding of the study revealed that there is significant difference were found in Occupational stress among male and female teachers and among Govt. and private secondary school teachers. The result indicates that no significant differences were found between Occupational Stress among urban area and rural area school teachers. The study also reveals strong negative correlation between the Occupational Stress and Job satisfaction of secondary school teachers of Sonipat District.

Keywords Occupational Stress, Job Satisfaction, Secondary School Teachers, Gender, Type of Institution, Geographical Location.

Introduction

Since ancient times, the place of teacher or guru has been considered paramount in Indian society. It is through teachers that intellectual traditions and technical skills are transferred from one generation to the next.

The work of a teacher is not only to provide education to their students but his job is also to provide all-round development of the child. The teacher also helps in the mental, intellectual and social development of the child. A teacher, as a motivator, is always helpful in showing the path to his students.

Actually, since ancient times, teaching has been viewed with great respect. There is always a feeling of respect for their teachers in the minds of students. Seeing this respect from his students, the teacher feels proud of himself and continues to do his work smoothly.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction provides a person with a sense of enjoyment and achievement, which increases the quality of work. When a person does his work without any stress or pressure, the productive capacity of that work also increases.

Job satisfaction is made up of two words: job and satisfaction. Work is the adjustment of duties and responsibilities and affects employees individually as a whole.

Satisfaction is a set of emotions and sensations. Most of the people, along with providing their means of livelihood, also develop their capabilities through jobs.

According to Block (1952) -

“Job satisfaction may be defined as an attitude that results from the balance and sum total of specific likes and dislikes experienced by an employee in a job.”

According to Locke -

“Job satisfaction can be defined as a pleasant emotional state that results from the evaluation of a job and makes it more convenient for the achievement of one's values.”

Job satisfaction refers to the general attitude developed by an employee towards his work. This is a type of motivation as a result of which the employee gets immense pleasure in doing his work smoothly. Job satisfaction is experienced at the individual level and cannot be interpreted collectively.

Job satisfaction is a pleasant and positive emotional feeling of a person. Which itself is less than the person's evaluation of his own work or work experiences. Job satisfaction is the result of many attitudes inherent in an employee. These attitudes are related only to work and are also related to many specific elements, such as remuneration, supervisor, continuity of employment, working conditions, promotion, etc., which definitely affect job satisfaction in some way or the other.

Employees who are satisfied with their work maintain their physical and mental balance. A physically and mentally healthy person motivates himself to work, his morale continuously increases. Due to which his work production capacity increases. It has been confirmed by many teachers that employees who are dissatisfied with their work also have less productivity.

Occupational Stress -

In today's scientific era, competition creates tension in every work. Management and relationships work effectively in every business. In every field, conflict of ideas and workload together create stress at the workplace.

The word stress is derived from the Latin word "stringere" which is used to denote, hard physical suffering, tension and adversity, which is caused by a physical part of the body or is generated by the environment or social situation. Whenever a situation of conflict arises between the individual and environmental demands, sometimes a situation of adjustment and maladjustment arises in front of the individual.

Meaning of Occupational stress -

The literal meaning of occupational stress is 'occupation related stress or stress related to occupation' i.e. stress arising after doing any work.

As we know that man is a social animal. He chooses some work to earn his livelihood. He chooses work according to his qualifications and capabilities. According to his educational qualifications, he chooses different types of professions like Doctor, Engineer, Professor, Teacher etc. While working at any workplace, some problems arise and until these problems are solved, the situation of tension persists. Thus, when stress arises related to business or work, it is called occupational stress.

According to Borg (1990)

“Not Fulfillment the demands of the workplace and inability to solve problems, failures, incompetence of teachers are among the reasons for stress.”

According to Wikipedia

“Occupational stress related to one's job. Occupational stress refers to a chronic condition. Occupational stress can be managed by understanding what stressful situations are in the workplace and taking steps to relieve those situations.”

According to Behar and Newman (1978)

“Occupational stress is a condition resulting from the interaction of people and their jobs and is characterized by changes occurring within people that force them to deviate from their normal functioning.”

Occupational stress can occur in anyone, no matter how good an employee he or she is. Teaching is seen as a 'noble profession'. In this profession also, various types of problems arise in front of a teacher. There are some problems which are not solved in time and then these problems become the cause of stress. In the teaching profession, apart from teaching, teachers are also given many tasks which, if not completed on time, create a situation of stress.

While observing the professional stress among teachers, Singh '2009' said that "Inability to complete the work on time, unclear instructions, inadequate facilities, unclear scrutiny of higher authorities, cooperation in the work of other people, excessive workload, lack of time." Also, lack of professional satisfaction is due to professional stress.

Finally, it can be said that job satisfaction helps in spreading pleasant and positive emotional feelings in the teacher. This is a motivation to the teacher by which he is able to do his work smoothly and gets pleasure in his profession. On the other hand, due to excess of work, stress arises at the workplace in the teaching profession due to which the teacher is unable to adjust himself physically, mentally and socially. Sometimes professional stress is considered good for getting good opportunities, but excess stress can be harmful for the mental health. Due to which his teaching work may be affected. Due to which his work performance may get hampered and his efficiency and work productivity may decline.

Objective of study

1. To study the Occupational Stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of gender.
2. To study the Occupational Stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of type of Institution.
3. To study the Occupational Stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of geographical location.
4. To find out the relationship between occupational stress and Job Satisfaction among secondary school teachers.

Review of Literature

Ali and Wasir (2018) conducted a study on “The effect of job satisfaction on teacher’s organizational commitment with special reference to private sector Universities of Punjab, Pakistan”. For this research work, 150 teachers were selected from different departments of Lahore Laid University and Lahore University located in Punjab district of Pakistan. In conclusion, it was found positivity and moderate correlation between job satisfaction and commitment with faculties.

Singh & Seema (2017) conducted a study on “The impact of Job Satisfaction on the attitude towards teaching among rural and urban area of Government school teachers” It was found in this study that there is no difference in teaching attitude and job satisfaction of rural and urban teachers. Teaching of teachers is not easily affected. Job satisfaction is only related to different parameters like type of schools, salary, working conditions, area (urban-rural) but teachers teaching attitude is not affected by these.

Chopra, Rita, and Garatia, Radha Kanta (2009) investigated the connection between secondary school teachers' accountability and occupational stress. In this study, researchers discovered that female instructors are more attentive to their duties than their male counterparts.

Methodology

A descriptive Survey type of research method was used for this study.

Sampling

A sample of 400 secondary school teachers was selected randomly from different secondary school of Sonipat District. The sample consists of both Govt. and Private sector.

Tools Used For fulfillment of the purpose of this study, two data collecting tools namely Occupational Stress Index and Job Satisfaction scale were used to collect raw data from the population. Following standardized test were used for collecting the data -

1. 'Occupational Stress Index' prepared by 'Dr. A.K. Srivastava and A.P. Singh'
2. 'Job Satisfaction Scale' prepared by 'Dr. Meera Dixit'

Variables of the study-

Two types of variables are included in the research work.

1. Independent Variable: Occupational Stress
2. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction.

Statistics Used in the Study

To draw an authentic interpretation descriptive statistical techniques namely mean, S.D, t-test and Correlation were applied.

Result and Discussion

Objective

1. To study the occupational stress of sec. school teachers on the basis of gender.

Table 1.1

Comparison of Occupational Stress of sec. school teachers on the basis of gender.

Gender	No. of Teachers	Mean	S.D.	D F	T-value	Significant level	Remark
Male	200	128.17	48.010	398	4.549	0.05	Significant
Female	200	110.88	24.202				

Figure 1.1

Interpretation -

Table and figure 1.1 indicates that the mean score of occupational stress of male and female teachers of secondary school are 128.17 and 110.88 with standard deviation 48.010 and 24.202 respectively. The t-value come out from the above two groups is 4.549 and the critical value of 't' at the level of significance is 1.96. Hence the t-value is greater then the critical value. Hence it is significant. Therefore the null Hypothesis "There is no significant difference between occupational stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of gender" was rejected at the significant level of 0.05.

Objective -2. To study the Occupational stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of type of Institution.

Table 1.2

Comparison of Occupational Stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of type of Institution.

Institution	No. of Teachers	Mean	S.D.	D F	T-value	Significant level	Remark
Govt.	200	102.57	28.703	398	9.661	0.05	Significant
Private	200	136.48	40.491				

Figure 1.2

Interpretation -

Table and figure 1.2 indicates that the mean score of Occupational stress of Govt. and Private secondary school teachers are 102.57 and 136.48 with standard deviations 28.703 and 40.491 respectively. The t-value come out from the above two groups is 9.661 and the critical value of 't' at the level of significance is 1.96. Hence the t-value is greater then the critical value. Hence it is significance. Therefore the null Hypothesis "There is no significant difference between Occupational stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of type of Institution" was rejected at the significance level of 0.05.

Objective-3 To study the Occupational Stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of geographical location.

Table 1.3

Comparision of Occupational Stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of geographical location.

Location	No. of Teachers	Mean	S.D.	DF	T-value	Significant level	Remark
Urban	200	119.85	40.986	398	0.165	0.05	Not Significant
Rural	200	119.20	36.892				

Figure 1.3

Interpretation -

Table and figure 1.3 reveals that the mean score of Occupational stress of urban area and rural area secondary school teachers are 119.85 and 119.20 with standard deviation 40.986 and 36.892 respectively. The t-value come out from the above two groups is 0.165 and the critical value of 't' at the level of significance of is 1.96. Hence the t-value is smaller then the critical value. Hence it is not significant. Therefore the null Hypothesis "There is no significant difference between Occupational stress of secondary school teachers on the basis of geographical location" was accepted at significant level of 0.05.

Objective-4 To find out the relationship between Occupational Stress and Job Satisfaction among secondary school teachers.

Table 1.4

The relationship between Occupational Stress and Job Satisfaction among secondary school teachers.

Variables	R	β	Significant Level	Result
Occupational Stress Vs Job Satisfaction	. 586	- . 586	0.001	Significant (Rejected)

Interpretation

It reveals that there is a significant relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers where R value is 0.586 and the β value is -0.586 which means there is a negative relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction i.e; β = -0.586 that means occupational stress leads to decline in job satisfaction by more than 58% . The significant value is less than 0.01 i.e; 0.001 which is significant and the null hypothesis "There is no significant relationship between occupational stress and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers." was rejected.

Findings

1. In the reference of Occupational stress of male and female teachers of secondary school of Sonipat District, the present study indicates that there is a significant difference in occupational stress among male and female teachers of secondary schools of Sonipat District. The mean value of male teachers is 128.17 which is more than the mean value of female teachers.
2. In regards to occupational stress between Govt. and private secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. The present study reveals that it was found that there is a significant

difference in occupational stress among Govt. and private secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. The mean value of private school teachers is 136.48 which is more than the Govt. teachers.

3. In regards to occupational stress between Urban and Rural area secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. The present study reveals that there is no significant difference in occupational stress among urban area and rural area secondary school teachers. The mean value of urban area and rural area school teachers are similar that is 119.85 and 119.20 respectively.

4. It was found that there is a significant relationship between occupational stress and Job Satisfaction of secondary school teachers of Sonipat District. It shows that there is a negative relationship between Occupational stress and Job Satisfaction among secondary school teachers of Sonipat District.

Conclusion

This study reveals that the position of teachers in relation to their occupational stress and Job satisfaction among secondary school teachers of District Sonipat. The mean indicates that male teachers have comparatively higher level of occupational stress as compared to female teachers. In comparison of Govt. and Private school teachers the Private school teachers bears higher level of occupational stress than the Govt. school teachers. But there is no difference will be found in Mean value of Urban and Rural area school teachers. It indicates that urban area school teacher's and rural area secondary school teacher's bears same level of Occupational stress. There is a significant and negative relationship will find in between Occupational stress and Job Satisfaction. It shows that Occupational stress influence by the level of Job Satisfaction of a teacher. If teacher is influenced by Occupational Stress He or she will not performed as good as He or She wants. It indicates that if teacher gets stress than the Job Satisfaction will be affected. Occupational Stress gives adverse effects on the work of teachers, students and other related staff involved in the teaching activities.

Limitation of the Study

- Delimitation of the study
1. This study was delimited to 400 secondary school teachers only.
 2. This study was confined to Sonipat District of Haryana only.

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